

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF THE ORIGIN OF STRESS IN MEDICINE

Nabiev Sherozbek

Andijan State Medical Institute, 5th year student of the Faculty of medicine

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6027937>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 15-dekabr 2021

Ma'qullandi: 15-yanvar 2022

Chop etildi: 5-fevral 2022

KALIT SO'ZLAR

Stress

Stress and Bad Stress.

Effects of stress overload

ABSTRACT

Modern life is full of frustration, deadlines. And demands. For people, stress is so commonplace that it has become a way of life. Stress isn't always bad, though. Stress within your comfort zone can help you perform under pressure; motivate you to do best, even keep you safe when danger looms. But when stress becomes overwhelming, it can damage your health, mood, relationships, and quality of life. You can protect yourself by understanding how the body's stress response works, recognizing the signs and symptoms of stress overload, and taking steps reduce its harmful effects.

Stress is your body's way of responding to any kind of demand or threat. When you feel threatened, your nervous system responds by releasing a flood of stress hormones, including adrenaline and cortisol, which rouse the body for emergency action. Your heart pounds faster, faster, muscles tighten, blood pressure rises, breath quickens, and your senses become sharper. These physical changes increase your strength and stamina, speed your reaction time, and enhance your focus. Good

Stress and Bad Stress. The stress response (also called the fight or flight response) is critical during emergency situation, such as when a driver has to slam on the brakes to avoid an accident. It can also be activated in a milder form at a time when the pressure's on the brakes to avoid an accident. It can also be activated in a milder form at a time when the pressure's on but there's no actual danger like

stepping up to take the foul shot that could win the game, getting ready to go to a big dance, or sitting down for a final exam. A little of this stress can help keep you on your toes, ready to rise to a challenge. And the nervous system quickly returns to its normal state, standing by to respond again when needed. But stress doesn't always happen in response to things that are immediate or that are over quickly. Ongoing or long-term events, like coping with a divorce or moving to a new neighborhood or that are over quickly. Ongoing or long-term events, like coping with a divorce or moving to a new neighborhood or school, can cause stress, too.

Long-term stressful situation can produce a lasting, low-level stress that's hard on people. The nervous system senses continued pressure and may remain slightly activated and continue to pump out extra stress hormones over an extended

period. This can wear out the body's reserves. leave a person feeling depleted or overwhelmed. weaken the body's immune system, and cause other problems.

Effects of stress overload. The body's autonomic nervous system often does a poor job of distinguishing between daily stressors and life-threatening events. If you're stressed over an argument with a friend, a traffic jam on your commute to work, or a mountain of bills. For example, your body can still react as if you're facing a life-or-death situation.

When you repeatedly experience the fight or flight stress response in your daily life, it can raise blood pressure, suppress the immune system, increase the risk of heart attack and stroke, speed up the aging process and leave you vulnerable to a host of mental and emotional problems.

Many health problems are caused or exacerbate by stress, including: Pain of kind, heart disease, digestive problems, sleep problems, depression. weight problems, autoimmune diseases, skin condition, such as eczema.

Signs and symptoms of stress overload. The following table lists some of the common warning signs and symptoms of chronic stress. The more signs and symptoms you notice in your you may be to stress overload.

Cognitive symptoms: memory problems, inability to concentrate. poor judgment, seeing only the negative, anxious or racing thoughts, constant worrying.

Emotional symptoms: moodiness, irritability or short temper, agitation, inability to relax feeling overwhelmed, sense of loneliness and isolation, depression or general unhappiness.

Physical symptoms: aches and pains, diarrhea or constipation, nausea, chest

pain, rapid heartbeat, loss sex drive. frequent colds.

Behavioral symptoms: eating more or less, sleeping too much or too little, isolating yourself from others, procrastinating or neglecting responsibilities, using alcohol. cigarettes, or drugs.

Keep in mind that the signs and symptoms of stress overload can also be caused by other psychological or medical problems. If you're experiencing any of the warning signs of stress, it's important to see A DOCTOR TO HELP DETERMINE IF YOUR SYMPTOMS ARE STRESS-RELATED.

Isolation and stress. Since social engagement appears to be our best defense against stress. isolation or lack of positive, consistent human interaction can be both a stressor in itself and exacerbate other causes of stress.

The situations and pressure that stress are known as stressors. We usually think of stressors as begin negative, such as an exhausting work schedule or rocky relationship. However, anything that puts high demands on you or forces you to adjust can be stressful. This includes positive events such as getting married, buying a house, going to college, or receiving a promotion.

Of course, not all stress is caused by external factors. Stress can also be self-generated, for external factors. Stress can also be self-generated, for example, when you worry excessively about something that may or may not happen. or have irrational, pessimistic thoughts about life.

1. *Common external causes of stress:* Major life changes, work or school. relationship difficulties. financial problems, being too busy, children and family.

2. *Common internal causes of stress:* Chronic worry, pessimism, negative self-talk, unrealistic expectation/perfectionism.

rigid thinking. lack of flexibility. all-or-nothing attitude.

What causes excessive stress depends, at least in part, on your perception of it. Something that's stressful to you may not faze someone else; they may even enjoy it. For example, your morning commute may make you anxious and tense because you worry that traffic will make you late. Others, however, may find the trip relaxing because they allow more than enough time and enjoy listening to music while they drive.

We're all different. Some people seem to be able to roll with life's punches, while others tend to crumble in the face of far smaller obstacles or frustrations. Some people even seem to thrive on the excitement and challenge of a high-stress lifestyle.

Your ability to tolerate stress depends on many factors, including the quality of your relationships and support network, your emotional intelligence, and genetics.

Factors that influence your stress tolerance: Your support network- Social engagement is the body's most evolved strategy for responding to stress so it's no surprise that people with a strong network of supportive friends and family members. are better able to cope with life's stressors. On the flip side, the more lonely, isolated you are, the less opportunity you have to utilize social engagement and the greater vulnerability to stress. Your exercise levels. Your physical and mental health are intrinsically linked, so the better you take care of your body, the greater resilience you'll have against the symptoms of stress. Exercising regularly (for 30 minutes or more on most days) can lift your mood and help relieve stress, anxiety. anger. and frustration. It can also serve as a distraction to your worries, allowing you to find some

quit time and break out of the cycle of negative thoughts that feed stress and anxiety. *Your diet.* The food you eat can also have a profound effect on your mood and how well you cope with life's stressors. Eating a diet full of processed and convenience food, refined carbohydrates, and sugary snacks can worsen of stress while eating a diet rich in fresh fruit and vegetables, high-quality protein, and healthy fats, especially omega-3 fatty acids, can help you better cope with life's ups and downs. *Your sense of control* - It may be easier to take stress in your stride if you have confidence in yourself and your ability to influence events and persevere through challenges. If you feel like things are out of your control. you're likely to have less tolerance for stress. *You attitude and outlook* - Optimistic people are often more stress-hardy. They tend to embrace challenges, have a strong sense of humor. And accept that challenge is a part of life. You ability to deal with your emotions You're extremely vulnerable to stress if you don't know how to calm and soothe yourself when you're feeling sad, angry, or overwhelmed by a situation. The ability to bring your emotions into balance help you bounce back from adversity and is a skill that can be learned at any age. You knowledge and preparation - The more you know about stressful situation, including how long it will last and what to expect. the easier it is to cope. For example, if you go into surgery with a realistic picture of what to expect post-op, a painful recovery will be less traumatic than if you were expecting to bounce back immediately.

How well do you handle stress in your life?

1. I have people I confide in when I'm feeling under pressure who make we feel better.

2. I feel comfortable expressing how I feel when something is bothering me.

3. In general, I fell in control of my life and confident in my ability to handle what comes my way.

4. I find reasons to laugh and feel grateful, even when going through difficulties.

5. No matter how busy I am, I make it a priority to sleep, exercise, and eat right.

6 I'm able to calm myself down when I start to feel overwhelmed.

References:

1. The book Stress survival. How to relax and live positively. Alix Krista. Foreword by Micheal van Straten. 2009 y. 201 pages.
2. 7 ways to prevent yourself becoming... Stressed- out, Over-worked & Run Down. 2012 y. 98 pages.
3. Stress Management. A Wellness Approach. Nanette E. Tummers 200 pages
4. The stress Solution. How to eliminate 75% Or more of you Stress without having to manage it. By Mort Orman, M.D. 2013y. 310page Keep in mind that the signs and symptoms are stress-related.

